

2-Thiopyrogallol : A New Spectrophotometric Reagent for Rhenium

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2-Thiopyrogallol reacts with rhenium(V) to give a violet colour complex formed by reducing ReO_4^- with the ligand itself at 9 N HCl. The complex has absorption maximum at 535 nm and is extractable into a mixture of *iso*-amyl alcohol and chloroform (1 : 9). Beer's law is obeyed from 0.25 to 16 ppm rhenium ($\epsilon = 1.58 \times 10^4$). With the exception of molybdenum and palladium, the method is free from usual interferences. The isolated complex has the composition $[\text{Re}(\text{LH})_2(\text{LH}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$; this is supported by elemental analysis, ir, conductance, ion-exchange and magnetic moment studies. By proper extension of Leden's method, the overall as well as stepwise formation constants for 1 : 3 system have been evaluated.

IN our search for new sensitive and selective organic reagents^{1,2} for spectrophotometric determination of rhenium, a new highly selective and sensitive reagent, 2-thiopyrogallol, has been developed based on the formation of a violet colour in 9 N HCl solution containing ReO_4^- . A few reagents like 8-mercaptoquinoline and its 6-chloro derivative ($\epsilon_{430} = 11,450$)³, thiosalicylic acid ($\epsilon_{410} = 6.1 \times 10^3$)⁴, 3-phenyl-5-(2-furyl)pyrazoline-1-carbodithioate ($\epsilon_{370} = 5.3 \times 10^4$)⁵, toluene-3,4-dithiol ($\epsilon_{692} = 23,250$)⁶ and dithioaniline ($\epsilon_{390} = 1.3 \times 10^4$)⁷ are considered promising reagents for spectrophotometric determination of rhenium. Of these 8-mercaptoquinoline has been proved to be a useful reagent for extraction and estimation of rhenium. The dithiol reagent⁶ has a reasonable degree of precision and sensitivity, but has interference from Cu, Ni, Co, W, Pt and Mo. Moreover, the method is much time consuming. The pyrazoline carbodithioate is a sensitive reagent for rhenium among organosulphur ligands but it suffers from serious interference.

2-Thiopyrogallol reacts with Re(IV) giving a green colour complex at 0.5-2.0 N HCl and with Re(V) at 9 N HCl giving a violet colour complex. This paper describes the detailed study of the violet complex as this is most sensitive and selective. The violet complex has absorption maximum at 535 nm, along with a very small absorption peak at 420 nm and is extractable into a mixture of *iso*-amyl alcohol and chloroform (1 : 9). Beer's law is obeyed over a concentration range 0.25 to 16 ppm of rhenium ($\epsilon = 1.58 \times 10^4$). With the exception of molybdenum and palladium, the method is essentially free from usual interferences. The complex has been isolated showing 1 : 3 metal to ligand ratio with the composition $[\text{Re}(\text{LH})_2(\text{LH}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ which has been supported by elemental analysis, ir, conductance, ion-exchange and magnetic studies. The stepwise formation constants have also been evaluated for the 1 : 3 system by extrapolation methods using spectrophotometric data.

Experimental

Apparatus : Visible spectral measurements were taken with a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer using matched 1.00 cm cells. A Perkin Elmer IR spectrophotometer, model 137 was used to record ir spectra using KBr disc. The magnetic studies were made on the Guoy apparatus.

Reagents : KReO_4 was obtained from Johnson-Mathey Co. (99.9% pure) and purity was checked by Nitron method⁸. Standard stock perrhenate solutions were prepared containing 1.00 mg of Re per ml. Desired solutions were prepared by proper dilution of the stock solutions. Chloroform was purified to free it from alcohol, and *iso*-amyl alcohol (A.R.) was distilled before use. A solution of *iso*-amyl alcohol and chloroform in 1 : 9 ratio was prepared for extraction work. The acidity of the aqueous phase was adjusted using hydrochloric acid (A.R.).

Preparation of the reagent : The reagent was prepared by the method of Pantlitschko and Benger⁹. Resorcinol (0.1 mole) and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (50 g) in water (250 ml) were treated with NH_4SCN (31 g) in water (50 ml). The colourless precipitate was filtered off. The filtrate was treated with 50 ml 1 M Na_2CO_3 solution and heated to boiling to produce 4-hydroxy-1,3(2H)-benzoxathiol-2-one (**1**) (yield 80%, m.p. 151°). 2-Thiopyrogallol was prepared by treating **1** (5 g) with 2 M NaOH (50 ml) in a nitrogen atmosphere. After 10 min, the solution was made weakly acid to congo red with dilute HCl and extracted with solvent ether when 2-thiopyrogallol separated as an oil which solidified to a yellowish crystalline mass. Vacuum sublimation gave white needles, m.p. 83-4°.

Recommended procedure : To an appropriate aliquot of the test solution containing 0.02-0.5 mg rhenium as ReO_4^- in a 50 ml separating funnel is added 7.5 ml of conc. HCl. The volume of the

aqueous phase is made upto 9 ml with water and 10 ml of extracting solvent is added. To this, 1 ml 0.4% (w/v) of the reagent solution is introduced and the mixture shaken thoroughly for 10 min. The organic layer is taken out over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The aqueous phase is washed with the solvent (2×5 ml) and the washings are mixed with the previous extracted fraction. The combined extract is transferred to a 25 ml calibrated flask and diluted upto the mark with the solvent. The absorbance of the complex is measured at 535 nm against solvent blank. Rhenium concentration is calculated from Beer's law ($\epsilon = 15896$).

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The visible absorption spectra of the solution of rhenium-2-thiopyragallol complex extracted according to the recommended procedure were studied from 360 to 620 nm and were found to be reproducible at different concentration of rhenium. The absorbance is maximum at 535-540 nm, with a small peak at 420 nm. As the reagent blank has no absorption at 535 nm the absorbances were taken at this wavelength against solvent blank throughout the studies.

Effect of variation in the amount of reagent: 1 ml of 0.4% (w/v) reagent was found to be sufficient for 8 ppm of rhenium. 7.5 ml of 12 N HCl in a total aqueous phase of 10 ml was necessary for quantitative extraction. *iso*-Amyl alcohol and chloroform in the ratio of 1 : 9 was found suitable for complete extraction. Shaking time of 5 min was needed for extraction. The extraction of the metal was found to be 99.8% in a single extraction.

Beer's law, molar absorptivity, sensitivity, optimum range and photometric error: A calibration curve of rhenium-2-thiopyragallol coloured complex was constructed and it was found that the system obeyed Beer's law over a concentration range 0.25 to 16 ppm of rhenium. The molar absorptivity of the complex calculated from Beer's law is 1.58×10^4 and the Sandell's sensitivity is $0.0117 \mu\text{g Re cm}^{-2}$. The optimum ranges and analytical accuracy obtained from Ringbom's curve was found to be from 2 to 12 ppm Re ml^{-1} . The percent relative error per 1% absolute photometric error according to Ayer's equation was found to be 2.7%.

Diverse ions: Interference of diverse cations and anions in the determination of rhenium was studied. A change of 0.005 in absorbance value was considered as the tolerance limit for reproducible results. Except for molybdenum and palladium, the method described here is free from interferences. The majority of ions reacting with the ligand (e.g. Pt^{4+} , V^{5+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and W^{6+}) have been tolerated at 9 M acidity and using higher concentrations of reagent (1 ml of 1% and in case of Cu^{2+} 1 ml of 2%). The molybdenum interference can be removed by ethyl xanthate-molybdate extraction¹⁰. The effect of diverse ions on the rhenium determination was studied by adding 400 ppm of the following ions to

a solution containing 8 ppm of Re as ReO_4^- and proceeding as in recommended procedure. Mn(II), Bi(III), Cd(II), Hg(II), Zn(II), Ca(II), Mg(II), Al(III), Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , F^- , NO_3^- , ClO_4^- , SO_4^{2-} , SCN^- , PO_4^{3-} , citrate, acetate, tartrate, oxalate and EDTA (in 50 fold excess) do not interfere.

Composition of the complex: The composition of the complex was determined by isolating the metal chelate, and calculating the step-wise formation constants by extension of Leden's method.

Isolation of the complex: In a 1 liter three necked flask 1 g KReO_4 is dissolved in 100 ml water, 370-375 ml conc. HCl is added and the solution is warmed on water bath. The reagent solution (0.056 M) is added to the acidic solution of perrhenate under N-atmosphere and stirred for 5 min. Immediately on addition of the ligand, violet coloured precipitates are formed. The flask is cooled to room temperature and the precipitate filtered in a sintered glass crucible, washed with a little warm water at least 3-4 times and dried under reduced pressure. The precipitate is dissolved in minimum amount of *iso*-amyl alcohol and filtered. Pet. ether ($40-60^\circ$) is added to the filtrate till precipitates separate out. The precipitated complex is filtered, washed with pet. ether containing a little *iso*-amyl alcohol, crystallized from ethyl acetate and stored under vacuum, m.p. decomposes above 280° , yield 1.8 g. (Found: Re, 29.7; C, 34.46; H, 2.59; S, 15.53. Calcd. for $\text{ReC}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7\text{S}_8$, $[\text{Re}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{LH})_2(\text{LH}_2)]$; Re, 29.78; C, 34.54; H, 2.40; S, 15.35%). The result indicates rhenium-2-thiopyragallol ratio to be 1 : 3.

A weighed quantity of the pure compound was dissolved in a known volume of 1 : 9 *iso*-amyl alcohol- CHCl_3 mixture and the absorption spectra observed. The visible spectra (380-620 nm) were the same as obtained in the analysis and extraction of rhenium by the recommended procedure, except for a small shifting of the major peak from 535 nm to 520 nm. The molar absorptivity value of rhenium calculated from the absorbance at 520 nm is in excellent agreement with that obtained for the complex in the recommended procedure, assuming 100% participation of rhenium in complex formation.

The sample of the pure complex was used for magnetic moment measurement in a Guoy apparatus. The complex was found to be diamagnetic, but after the diamagnetic corrections the effective paramagnetic moment for the rhenium was found as 0.1-0.3 B.M. This excludes the possibility of 4+ and 6+ oxidation states which have high magnetic moments and suggests that the rhenium is in 5+ state (normal moment between 0.1 and 0.6 B.M.).

Step-wise formation constants: The procedure for evaluation of the step-wise formation constants were the graphical extrapolation method of Leden¹¹. The values for the free ligand concentrations were calculated for each determination of absorbance values from reagent effect and Beer's law data. The successive stability constants were

obtained by considering the degree of complex formation function¹¹ for 1 : 3 complex. The values are :

$$k_1 = 7.0 \times 10^3$$

$$k_2 = 1.4 \times 10^3$$

and $k_3 = 2.05 \times 10^4$

Thus the positive value of β_3 also confirms the existence of metal complex of 1 : 3 composition. The order of stability constants has been found to be $k_3 > k_1 > k_2$, which may be attributed to the protonation of the metal complex formed after or before the formation of the 1 : 3 species.

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